

A data-driven approach for the assessment of the thermal stratification of reservoirs based on readily available data

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ABSTRACT

A data-driven approach to assess the occurrence of thermal stratification and the depth of the thermocline in water masses has been developed and tested in the Spanish reservoir of El Val. The novelty of this approach is that it relies only on readily available data that can be collected for almost any reservoir, providing water managers with a transferable tool that can be easily adapted for any other reservoirs or lakes. The input variables were meteorological data, the water level and the output flow. A non-supervised clustering technique, *k-means*, was used to identify the stratification period with unlabelled data, that is to say inferring patterns when data from the target variable is not available. As a supervised method, Artificial Neural Networks were used to classify a given day as having or not having stratification and, in the positive case, to infer the depth of the thermocline. The classification showed a very high accuracy (96%) and the estimation of the thermocline depth showed a mean absolute error (MAE) of 1.94 m and 1.99 m in the training and test fractions, respectively. Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP) values were used to improve the explainability and they revealed that the most important features to infer the depth of the thermocline were the water level, the daily average solar irradiance and the air temperature.

1. Introduction

Large water bodies like oceans, lakes and reservoirs show thermal stratification during the warm and/or hot periods along the year in most climate zones on Earth, or even can remain permanently stratified (Boehrer and Schultze, 2008). Thermal stratification regulates the vertical movement of nutrients (Noori et al., 2021), dissolved oxygen, and other chemical species (Ding et al., 2022; Kusakabe et al., 2008; Xiao et al., 2022), which can influence the growth and distribution of phytoplankton, zooplankton, and fish populations (Lofton et al., 2022). More recently, the vertical distribution of emerging substances of concern, such as microplastics, are being studied in reservoirs (Zhang et al., 2023).

The main reason for this stratification is the warming of the upper layer due to factors such as air temperature and solar radiation. The increase of temperature in the upper layer (epilimnion) reduces its density and therefore, remains separated from the bottom layer (hypolimnion). The intermediate layer that separates both parts is called metalimnion, where the temperature changes abruptly in a zone called *thermocline*, whose position (depth) and temperature varies along the

stratification period. To understand the ecological significance of stratification in reservoirs, it is crucial to accurately detect and monitor their conditions: the duration and timing as well as the position and strength of the thermocline. Detecting the presence of the thermocline and its depth is important for different reasons, like those related to the management of water bodies (i.e. optimizing reservoir operation, informing water resource planning, etc.) (Casamitjana et al., 2003; Mi et al., 2019) as well as to the study of the impacts of weather patterns and climate change (Wang et al., 2024a). Focusing on reservoirs that are the main source of water supply for human consumption, irrigation, and industrial use, the stratification can impact its availability and quality.

Over the years, various methods have been developed to assess the timing, duration and intensity of stratification, ranging from traditional field measurements to advanced remote sensing techniques. The most basic but effort consuming method is the collection of in-situ measurements. It provides valuable information, especially when the data are collected with high-frequency (Liu et al., 2019; Wagner et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2022). Nonetheless, the recent improvements in communications technologies have made possible the design of more sophisticated methods for in-situ monitoring, reducing the human involvement

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in the data collection process. As a recent example, [Sun et al. \(2022\)](#) developed a floating platform which collects and process the information in real time, what they called management assistant for stratified reservoirs (MASR).

Remote sensing techniques are gaining popularity in the last years with the advancement of sensor technology (i.e. the improvement of their resolution) and processing algorithms. They allow monitoring areas of difficult access, like mountainous ones or conflict zones. Thermal infrared (TIR) sensors onboard satellites can measure the surface temperature of water bodies ([Reinart and Reinhold, 2008](#); [Pareeth et al., 2017](#)), which can provide information on the spatial distribution and temporal dynamics of the thermocline ([Curtarelli et al., 2015](#)). Airborne sensors, such as thermal imaging cameras or airborne laser scanners (LIDAR), can also be used to remotely measure water surface temperature.

When the objective is to make predictions, modelling techniques are usually implemented. Numerical models, such as hydrodynamic models connected with heat flux models, can simulate the thermal structure of water masses based on inputs such as meteorological data, bathymetry, discharges and initial conditions. There exist different approaches depending on the dimensionality: one dimensional (1D), two dimensional (2D) or three dimensional (3D). Each of them has its advantages and limitations, and their selection usually depends on the specific objective of the simulation, the water body characteristics and the availability of computer resources ([Ishikawa et al., 2022](#)). On the one hand, 3D models allow for a high spatial detail at the expense of a high computational demand. Their main disadvantages are related to the need of hard to collect input data, like the bathymetry, and physical parameters. Some examples are the FLOW module of Delft3D (Deltares), MIKE 3 Flow Model FM (DHI) or Fantom Refined ([Duka et al., 2021](#)).

On the other hand, 1D models are computationally lighter and require less parameters, and have demonstrated to be useful to represent the thermal stratification in water bodies. As recent examples of its implementation, [Wang et al., 2023](#) used the WRF-Lake model to simulate the stratification of a deep lake and [Li et al., 2022](#) used the Dynamic Reservoir Simulation Model (DYRESM) to simulate and predict the variation of water temperature, along with depth and time, for the Xin'anjiang Reservoir. In the middle term, 2D models are an interesting choice, especially when transversal flow processes are not crucial. One of the most popular is CE-QUAL-W2 ([Cole and Buchak, 1995](#)), with recent examples of its implementation for the simulation of thermal stratification ([Noori et al., 2019](#); [Yaghouti et al., 2023](#)). Among the most valuable characteristics of numerical models are their interpretability and their usefulness in prospective analysis, as featured in the implementation made by [Prats et al., 2017](#), where different management strategies under climate change scenarios were simulated using the 1D model EOLE and in the optimization of withdrawal strategies through the simulation with CE-QUAL-W2 in [Wang et al., 2024b](#).

Data-driven models are an alternative type of models, among which machine learning and deep learning (ML and DL) models stand out in recent years. According to [Lee et al. \(2023\)](#) data-driven models applied to freshwater ecosystems have been mainly focused on phytoplankton, while there is a lack of research in modelling future changes, such as climate change and subsequent changes in habitat conditions. A good example of a data-driven model focused on algal blooms prediction is that presented by [Miura et al. \(2023\)](#). Nonetheless, there are several examples in the scientific literature about ML or DL models designed to predict the temperature profile in water masses. [Liu and Chen \(2012\)](#) developed ML models based on Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) using as inputs meteorological conditions to predict the temperature in the 3

Fig. 1. Map of the study site. Made with QGIS, data by OpenStreetMap.

upper meters of a lake. Although they obtained better results when they used numerical models, they recognised that ANN can be developed with much less effort and that they can be used as a cost-effective and easy-to-use tool. The low performance of the ANN may be attributed to the short duration of the period represented by the training data. [Saber et al. \(2020\)](#) developed a model for long-term forecasting of several water quality variables at different depths, but the forecasting is not influenced by its contemporary meteorological conditions, therefore its use to assess the behaviour under the incoming climate change conditions may be limited.

The aim of this work is to provide the water resource managers with a tool that allows a quick estimation of the thermal state of a lake or reservoir, thus supporting management decisions. The tool is based on DL models that rely only on readily available variables, often available online as open data, so that the proposed approach could be easily transferred to other reservoirs with a relatively low investment. As stated by [Miura et al. \(2023\)](#) referring to algal blooms but also applicable to thermal stratification, these are highly site-specific phenomena, which makes it difficult to develop a comprehensive model that can be universally applied for different sites under varied meteorological and environmental conditions. In this particular case, the data used as input must fulfil the requirements of keeping a relationship with the phenomenon under study, in this case the thermal stratification, as well as being readily available in both past (observed) and future (forecasted) situations. The main variables that fulfil these requirements are meteorological data, which can be accompanied by other variables related to the storage state and operation of the reservoir. Practitioners responsible for modelling in each specific study site should consider what variables are relevant and include them if available.

An unsupervised ML model was implemented to assist in determining the threshold of the thermal gradient to consider if the reservoir is stratified or not. Then, two supervised DL models were designed in order to forecast the stratification status of the reservoir, as well as the depth of the thermocline in case it was stratified.

This approach is aligned with the Open Science paradigm, which has seen a significant boost in recent years especially in the context of Open Data. Much effort is being put into providing useful data, which in most cases is under-utilised. New ways of using this data need to be developed to accelerate research and stimulate innovation and this is precisely an aspect to stress in this work: the use of open data sources that are common and easy to obtain for the design of models capable of providing useful information.

2. Methods

2.1. Study site

In this work, the monitoring data of El Val reservoir (province of Zaragoza, Spain), which is managed by the Ebro Hydrographic Confederation (in Spanish: Confederación Hidrográfica del Ebro (CHE)), were used. Its main tributary is El Val River, but it also receives water from the Queiles River through a pipeline and from several ravines. The dam releases on the Queiles River, which is a tributary of the Ebro River (the second one in Spain in length and discharge rate). The maximum water level reaches 620 m above the sea level (m.a.s.l.), where occupies 112 ha, and it has a maximum depth of 66 m and a mean depth of 45 m. The El Val reservoir is part of the Registry of Protected Areas according the Article 6 of the Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC), within the categories of areas of water extraction for human consumption and areas of habitats or species protection, ZEPA "Sierra de Moncayo - Los Fayos -Sierra de Armas" (Natura 2000 Network, code: ES0000297). In spite of this protection, El Val reservoir has been suffering diverse eutrophication episodes, generally presenting mesotrophic and eutrophic levels and in some cases chlorophyll-a concentration reached hypereutrophic levels ([Confederación Hidrográfica del Ebro, 2018](#); [Confederación Hidrográfica del Ebro, 2019](#)). A map of the reservoir area

and its location in Spain is shown in [Fig. 1](#).

2.2. Data gathering

The CHE openly shares the monitoring data of El Val reservoir through the web page of the Ebro Automatic Water Quality Information System (SAICA Ebro by its initials in Spanish).¹ The El Val reservoir holds a self-positioning multiparameter probe (aquaDam, Adasa Systems), which began to record data in 2018. It is hanging from a structure in the dam and every 6 h, starting at noon in GMT time (1:00 p.m. in winter time, 2:00 p.m. in summer), the probe makes a vertical profile taking the measurements at each metre of depth from the surface to approximately 573 m.a.s.l., that is to say, between 2 and 3 m above the bottom outlet. The dam has its bottom outlet at the height of 570.78 m.a.s.l. and the bottom of the dam reaches 539.00 m.a.s.l.. The aquaDam probe collects data of the following variables: temperature (°C), pH, oxidation-reduction potential (mV), conductivity ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$), dissolved oxygen (mg L^{-1}), turbidity (NTU) and chlorophyll concentration ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$). Among these data, in this work the temperature data from 2018 to 2022 were used in order to calculate the existence of thermal stratification and, in positive cases, the depth and temperature of the thermocline.

The Ebro Automatic Hydrographic Information System (SAIH Ebro by its initials in Spanish)² provides other variables related to El Val reservoir, in particular meteorological variables, reservoir storage state variables and the flow rate of the Queiles River downstream of the dam. In particular, data from the weather station of El Val (code EM71), the monitoring station of the reservoir storage state (code E071) and the Queiles River gauge station (code A174) were used. Regarding meteorological data, the following variables were gathered: the daily minimum (AirTempMin), maximum (AirTempMax) and average air temperature (AirTempAvg) (°C), the daily average wind speed (Wind) (m s^{-1}), the daily maximum (RadMax) and average (RadAvg) solar irradiation (W m^{-2}) and the daily cumulative precipitation (Rain) (L m^{-2}). Regarding the storage state, the data of daily water level (Level) (m.a.s.l.) were gathered. Finally, the flow rate of the Queiles River a few meters downstream of the dam (Flow) ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$) was also gathered. No input flow rate was available, nonetheless the inflow by itself, without its temperature, may be useless. The relationship between the flow and the water temperature in the rivers of the Ebro River basin has been recently studied ([Lorenzo-González et al., 2023](#)) and it was reported that, although in general the water temperature decreases with higher flows, this relation is weak ($R^2 < 0.5$), therefore the inclusion of the inflows is not representative of the temperature flux entering from the river.

These nine available variables will be the independent variables in the models. All of them keep a relationship with the thermal stratification of a reservoir in different ways, that are briefly summarised as follows. Air temperature affects the thermal properties of the water body and can indirectly influence the occurrence and depth of the thermocline ([Noori et al., 2023](#)). Higher air temperatures can lead to higher surface water temperatures, which can result in a more pronounced thermocline. Conversely, lower air temperatures can cool the surface water and reduce the strength or depth of the thermocline. Wind and currents can affect the occurrence and depth of the thermocline by influencing the vertical mixing of water in the reservoir. Strong winds can increase surface turbulence, promoting vertical mixing and potentially deepening the thermocline ([Wang et al., 2024c](#)). Although wind direction is also an important factor, it has not been included due to its high variability throughout the day, making its integration on a daily basis highly unrealistic. Solar radiation is another major driving force behind the formation and maintenance of the thermocline. During

¹ <https://saica.chebro.es>

² <http://www.saihebro.com>

Fig. 2. Violin plots of the original input features.

periods of high solar radiation, the surface water is heated, leading to a warm surface layer. This warm surface layer tends to be less dense and forms a stable layer that inhibits the vertical mixing of water, resulting in the development of the thermocline. Regarding the rain, it has been observed that moderate and heavy rainfall events could reduce the thermal stability of the water column, this deepening the mixing layer depth (Liu et al., 2020). Finally, the depth of the reservoir can also affect the occurrence and depth of the thermocline. In shallow reservoirs, the thermocline may be closer to the surface due to increased heat exchange with the atmosphere and reduced vertical mixing. In deeper reservoirs, the thermocline may be deeper due to increased water volume and reduced influence of surface heating. Besides the direct relationship between the water level and the stratification, it should be noted that it also acts as a proxy of the water volume and the water surface exposed to solar radiation and water-air interaction. Finally, the outlet flow rate is related to the mixing and turbulence in the water mass.

The ordinary day of the year was also considered as independent variable but finally it was not included. Although it could improve the results of the models, as observed by Yousefi and Toffolon (2022) in the prediction of lake surface water temperature, it could be detrimental in case of using the models to make predictions under different climate scenarios where the meteorological conditions in a certain day can be very different from the conditions from which the model has learned for the same day of the year. As an example, if we wanted to know the depth of the thermocline in an atypical hot May, the variable of the day of the year would force the model to predict something similar to a typical May, in other words, to what it has learned that usually happens in May.

2.3. Data analysis framework

Data analysis was performed using open source libraries and frameworks for the Python 3 programming language. The main libraries that were used and their versions are: NumPy 1.23.5, SciPy 1.9.1, Pandas 1.4.4, Scikit-Learn 1.02, Keras 2.12.0 and Shap 0.42.1. The specific functions used are indicated in the text where relevant. This Python-based environment was chosen due to its growing usage trend for data analytics, being also suitable as a general-purpose programming language (Nguyen et al., 2019).

2.4. Data pre-processing

The first step consisted of a preliminary screening of the data in order to check the general quality, which was appropriate enough for this work as the data are supervised by the CHE before their publication through the SAICA and the SAIH. It is worth mentioning that the data from April 2020 were not available, presumably due to the lockdown

Fig. 3. Scheme of thermal behaviour as a function of depth in a stratified reservoir.

caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. Next, the four available daily profiles were averaged in order to obtain one profile per day. For this purpose, the depth data were rounded to integer values and then the four daily profiles were averaged by depth, resulting in a total of 1695 profiles along the 5 years. After visual inspection of the profiles, 8 of them were removed manually due to noteworthy erroneous values, leaving 1687 profiles. A visual inspection of the data from the different features allowed detecting 21 observations that were obviously erroneous as they were isolated points that clearly stood out from the rest and it was not necessary to apply any other methods.

In order to increase the information provided to the models, a feature augmentation process was carried out by including lagged features, which is very common when dealing with time series, as it provides the model with information about the previous days. For each observation, the input features of the 1 to 5 previous days were added, which means that each row of the dataset contains the information of the same day as well as the information of the five previous days. Each variable is named

after the original variable, followed by the number of days lagged.

Finally, observations with missing data (NaN values) were removed because they were only 10 and it was not worth implementing a filling method (5 of them were the 5 first observations, as their lagged features could not be calculated for them).

The main statistical descriptors of the numerical variables included in the models are shown in Table A1 in the appendix while the violin plots are shown in Fig. 2. An individual plot representing the evolution of each variable along the 5 years under study is presented in the Appendix.

2.5. Data analysis and modelling

2.5.1. Thermal stratification assessment

The temperature profiles were used to assess the thermal behaviour of the reservoir and then determine the stratification periods and the depth of the thermocline when it existed. With this purpose, the empirical function proposed in Rimmer et al. (2005) and corrected in (Cook and Rimmer, 2010) (Eq. (1)), that describes the relationship between the temperature and depth in a thermally stratified water body, was applied to determine the position of the inflexion point (Z) of each daily averaged temperature profile (Fig. 3), where the metalimnion is located.

Eq. (1) is shown below, where α and n are parameters related to the height and thickness of the metalimnion and were obtained through non-linear least squares fitting of Eq. (2) using the *scipy* function “*curve_fit*”. T_e is the epilimnion upper layer temperature and T_h is the hypolimnion lower layer temperature.

$$T(z) = T_h + \frac{T_e - T_h}{(1 + (\alpha Z)^n)^m} \quad (1)$$

$$Z = \frac{1}{\alpha} m^{(1-m)} \quad (2)$$

$$m = 1 - \left(\frac{1}{n} \right) \quad (3)$$

The equation that represents the thermal profile for each day was obtained and the value of Z was calculated. Then, the temperatures 0.5 m above and below Z were calculated in order to know the thermal gradient along 1 m with centre in Z . As a result of this calculation, a numeric variable that stored the depth of the thermocline (Z) was added to the dataset. In order to find a threshold to consider when the reservoir is stratified or not, which is often obtained empirically with values ranging from 0.2 to 2 °C m⁻¹ (Zhang et al., 2022), the distribution of the thermal gradient along the time was studied.

2.5.2. Unsupervised clustering

In this work, an unsupervised ML model was implemented to create two clusters of observations as a function of the selected independent variables. The intuition behind this approach is that the clusters created might coincide with the periods of stratification and mixing. We used the *k-means* algorithm through its implementation with the library *Scikit-Learn*. This algorithm separates the observations in the indicated number of clusters by trying to reduce the variance within clusters. Once the data were separated in two clusters, which were called *Cluster 0* and *Cluster 1*, we studied how the thermal gradient was distributed between them. This allowed to tag the observations as susceptible to cause thermal stratification or not.

The result of this process was added to the dataset as a new categorical binary variable that stored the existence of stratification or not (took the value of 0 when the reservoir was not stratified and 1 when it was stratified).

2.5.3. Forecasting ML models

A classification model was designed in order to detect if there existed

Table 1
Initial hyperparameters space.

Initial hyperparameters space	
Hyperparameters	Values
Layers	1 dense layer, 1 dense layer +1 dropout layer
Number of neurons of the dense layer	32, 64
Dropout rate of the dropout layer	0.2, 0.4
Learning rate	10 ⁻³ , 10 ⁻⁴
Batch size	32, 64

thermal stratification in the reservoir or, on the contrary, it was mixed; while in order to calculate the depth of the thermocline, a regression model was designed. Among the variety of available ML algorithms to perform classification and regression tasks, ANN were chosen to address the problem presented in this work. They are supervised ML models, which means that both, the independent and dependent variables, are shown to the model to learn from them.

An ANN is composed of layers of neurons connected among them. The ANN architecture implemented in this work includes sequential *dense layers* and *dropout layers*. Dense layers are those in which each neuron of a layer is connected to all the neurons of the previous layer. Each neuron receives a stimulus (an input) which is processed to produce a response (an output). This processing consists of assigning a weight to each input. Once these weights are calculated, the product of each input and its associated weight (plus a bias) is added, and then an activation function must be applied to obtain the output. Dropout layers are used to prevent overfitting and they work by randomly setting the inputs to 0 with a given frequency rate, which is another hyperparameter to tune, at each step during the training. Each dense layer has an associated activation function. As activation function, the widely known Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) was used, except in the output layer of the ANN for classification, which uses the sigmoid function with a threshold of 0.5. This means that the outputs with a value lower than 0.5 belong to one of the classes of the binary classification, while the outputs with a value equal or higher than 0.5 belong to the other class. In this work, ANN were implemented using the *keras* library.

In order to find the optimal combination of hyperparameters while avoiding the risk of over-fitting the models, we performed *k-fold cross-validation*. In this method the training set is split into k fractions, each one being used iteratively as a validation set, while the remaining $k-1$ fractions are used as training set. Therefore, the validation process is performed k folds or times, with a different validation set each time. In all the models the first 4 years (2018-2021) were used as training set while the last year (2022) was used as test set, thus meaning a proportion of approximately 80–20%, which is a common rule in ML. Given this data structure, it was found to be consistent to choose a value of k equal to 4, so that each validation fraction corresponds approximately to one year.

Opposite to other families of ML models that have a narrow range of hyperparameters to adjust, ANN are defined by different types of hyperparameters, which together with the computational cost of training deep ANN, restricts the options to optimize. On the one hand, we have the hyperparameters that define the architecture of the ANN (number of layers and number of neurons), while on the other hand we have the hyperparameters that control the training process (mainly the learning rate, the optimizer, the batch size and the number of epochs that the training lasts). In order to avoid an exhaustive search that could consume a lot of time, a small dimensional space was initially defined and explored with the original variables. The initial hyperparameters that composed this space are shown in Table 1. The number of epochs was maintained in 500 as it proved to guarantee the stabilization of the loss curves during the training. As optimizer, the Adam algorithm was used, which is a stochastic gradient descent method. Then, one of the hyperparameters was modified iteratively following the direction that

Fig. 4. Temperature gradient along 1 m with centre in Z between 2018 and 2021.

made an improve, until no improvements were reached. As examples, these modifications consisted on the multiplication of the neurons of the dense layer and the addition of dense layers with half of the neurons of the previous one.

The process followed with the addition of the lagged variables from 1 to 5 days iteratively, and the search for the best set of hyperparameters each time. Finally, the best combination of features and hyperparameters was chosen to refit the models on the whole training data.

2.5.3.1. Classification model to detect the thermal stratification. In this model the binary variable that stores the existence of stratification or not was defined as the target, while the independent variables mentioned in Section 2.2 were defined as the predictors. The variables were scaled before being passed to the model by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance in order to avoid the effect that the different scale of the variables could have on the results.

The selection of the best set of hyperparameters was made according to three commonly used metrics: the binary accuracy, the recall calculated as in Eq. (4), where TP is the number of true positives and FN is the number of false negatives, and the area under the ROC (Receiver Operating Characteristics) curve (AUC).

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}} \quad (4)$$

The binary accuracy computes the frequency with which the predicted target variable matches the true one. The recall represents, from the positive classes, how many are predicted correctly. Finally, the AUC gives information about how much the model is able to distinguish between classes. The AUC maximum value is 1 and the higher this value is, the better the model is.

Once the best model for each set of features (i.e. each iteration with the addition of the lagged variables) was determined, they were refitted on the whole training set and tested on the unseen test data. The same metrics than during the cross-validation process were computed.

2.5.3.2. Regression model to estimate the depth of the thermocline. In this model the numeric variable that stores the depth of the thermocline (Z), calculated as shown in Eq. (2), was the target, while the independent variables mentioned in Section 2.2 were defined as the predictors. As in the case of the classification model, the variables were scaled.

In this case, the procedure to design and train the ANN regression models was similar than that of the classification models. It began with the definition of a small topology with the scaled original variables as inputs. In this case, the metric monitored along the training process was the mean absolute error (MAE). Identically to the classification model,

once the best model for each set of features was chosen, they were refitted on the whole training set and tested on unseen test data. The test MAE was also obtained.

In order to assess the contribution of the variables to the performance of the models the Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP) values (Lundberg and Lee, 2017) were used. In their calculation, a comparison between the models' predictions with and without a particular feature is done iteratively for each feature and each observation. The SHAP values are a way to compute how much each variable has contributed to the actual prediction, whether positively or negatively. Positive SHAP values involves an increase in the predicted variables, while negative SHAP values involves a decrease. Therefore, the SHAP values are useful to quantify features importance, considering that the features with the largest mean absolute Shapley values are the most important. The SHAP analysis has been previously used together with ML modelling to assess the influence of environmental factors like climate variability on lagoon ecosystem parameters in Lake Vistula (Kruk, 2023; Kruk et al., 2021).

3. Results

3.1. Thermal stratification assessment and clustering

The occurrence of stratification in El Val reservoir was evaluated as described in Section 2.5.1. Fig. 4 shows the evolution of the thermal gradient along 1 m with centre in Z during the four training years. It can be seen that each year, with the exception of 2018, the gradient gradually increases until it reaches a peak, from which it decreases until it reaches a turning point from which the gradient makes a sharp peak. This kind of evolution with an intensification at the end of the stratification period, is attributed to the currents originated by the bottom outlet (Pérez-Villar, 2021). In fact, among the years studied, 2018 is the only one in which this phenomenon did not take place, which coincides with the only year in which the water level in the reservoir did not drastically decrease during the autumn, as shown in Fig. A8.

In sight of the values of the thermal gradient, it can be concluded that the beginning and the end of the stratified period occur when the thermal gradient is approximately $0.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C m}^{-1}$. In the plot, the results from the clustering process are also shown, with different colours for the days that are grouped in each cluster. It was calculated that 95.3% of the observations included in Cluster 0 by the unsupervised clustering algorithm *k-means* have a gradient above $0.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C m}^{-1}$. Regarding Cluster 1, it includes 75.5% of the observations that have a gradient under $0.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C m}^{-1}$. Among the 24.5% of the observations that have a gradient above this value but are included in Cluster 1, the observations belonging to the period when the thermocline originated by the outlet current occurs

Fig. 5. Depth of the thermocline between 2018 and 2021.

Table 2

Results from the training and testing of the selected classification model for each set of variables.

Variables	Hyperparameters				Training			Testing		
	Topology*	Learning rate	Batch size	Epochs	Acc.	Recall	AUC	Acc.	Recall	AUC
t	32(0.2)	10^{-4}	32	390	0.89	0.89	0.97	0.93	0.94	0.97
+ t-1	32(0.4)	10^{-4}	32	340	0.92	0.91	0.97	0.93	0.96	0.98
+ t-2	32(0.4)	10^{-4}	32	300	0.92	0.91	0.98	0.96	0.97	0.98
+ t-3	32(0.4)	10^{-4}	32	300	0.92	0.92	0.98	0.96	0.97	0.99
+ t-4	32(0.2), 16(0.2)	10^{-4}	32	200	0.94	0.93	0.99	0.96	0.98	0.99
+ t-5	32(0.4), 16(0.2)	10^{-4}	32	190	0.92	0.92	0.99	0.97	0.99	1.00

* The number of neurons in successive dense layers is separated by a comma, with the dropout rate in parentheses if a dropout layer existed after a dense layer.

are found. Considering that the input variables are mainly meteorological ones, it is coherent that the algorithm is able to identify the period of thermal stratification that is attributable to the meteorological conditions, but not the period that is attributable to the bottom currents. It is worth highlighting that this approach allows approximating the occurrence of thermal stratification in the reservoir without the need of physico-chemical monitoring.

Considering the threshold of $0.3 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C m}^{-1}$, in 2018 the stratification period began on April 16th and ended clearly on October 29th, with a duration of 196 days. In the next year, 2019, the stratification began on March 11th and the turning point occurred on October 6th. The stratification disappeared completely on November 7th, which means a duration of 241 days. Next year's data, 2020, is some troublesome, which is attributed to the lockdown caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. The stratification period seems to have started during the lockdown, as the next available profile, on May 8th, presents a thermal gradient higher than $0.3 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C m}^{-1}$. The stratification remained until October 27th, with the turning point on September 29th. Finally, in 2021 the stratification began on March 27th and ended on November 3rd, which means that it had duration of 221 days.

The depth of the thermocline was calculated according to Eqs. (1) and (2) after having applied the threshold of $0.3 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C m}^{-1}$ to consider a day as stratified, whose results are plotted in Fig. 5. It allows seeing how the thermocline usually is formed in the upper-intermediate layers, then moves upwards and finally goes downwards and disappears. This movement of the thermocline from intermediate layers to the bottom is what it is hypothesised to occur as a consequence of the aforementioned bottom currents.

As a result of the study of the thermal gradient, a variable storing the presence of stratification in the reservoir along the time was created. It took the value of 0 when the reservoir was not stratified (the thermal gradient was lower than $0.3 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C m}^{-1}$) and the value of 1 when the reservoir was stratified (the thermal gradient was equal or higher than

$0.3 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C m}^{-1}$).

3.2. Detection of thermal stratification through classification

In this section the results from the classification models described in section 2.5.3.1 are presented, which were used to detect the occurrence of thermal stratification in the reservoir using only meteorological variables, the level and the outlet flow data as input. In this case, the difference with the unsupervised model is that the models use the target variable to learn, therefore a period of water temperature monitoring is needed to get the training data.

Table 2 contains the best set of hyperparameters found for each set of variables, together with the results from the training on the whole training data set and test on unseen data. During the cross-validation process, there were no discrepancies among the three metrics used. Generally, the best model for each set of variables was optimal regarding the three metrics or the differences were $<1\%$. In case of these small discrepancies, the model with the highest AUC was chosen. The first row in Table 2, represented as *t* in the column of variables, contains the results of the model with only variables that are contemporaneous with the target. The row represented as + *t-1* contains the variables in *t* and the 1-day lagged variables, and so on in the following rows. The number of epochs was adjusted to the minimum number of epochs that guaranteed the stabilization of the loss curve in the four folds of the cross-validation.

For the models with up to 3 days-lagged variables, a single dense layer with 32 neurons was the optimal topology. Although the models did not present a pronounced trend to overfit, in general they performed better when a dropout layer was added after the dense layer. Finally, when 4 and 5 days-lagged variables were included, the model benefited from the addition of an additional dense layer followed by another dropout layer. According to the results, in general the training metrics improved as lagged variables were added, however when the 5 days-

Table 3
Confusion matrix for the training and test predictions with the optimal classification model.

		Predicted classes			
		Training		Testing	
		Not-stratified	Stratified	Not-stratified	Stratified
True classes	Not-stratified	549	31	115	7
	Stratified	53	681	2	166

Fig. 6. Real and predicted values of thermocline presence with the optimal classification model. The points at the left of the dashed line belong to the training set while those at the right belongs to the test set.

Table 4
Results from the training and testing of the selected regression model for each set of variables.

Variables	Hyperparameters				Training			Testing		
	Topology*	Learning rate	Batch size	Epochs	MAE	Percentile	P ₅₀	MAE	Percentile	P ₅₀
t	32(0.4)16(0.2)8	10 ⁻³	32	500	2.42	67.6	1.47	2.47	65.5	1.54
+ t-1	32(0.4)	10 ⁻³	32	80	2.70	66.9	1.66	2.63	66.7	1.55
+ t-2	32(0.2)4(0.2)	10 ⁻³	32	250	2.44	70.4	1.26	2.28	70.8	1.23
+ t-3	32(0.2)4(0.2)	10 ⁻³	32	280	1.94	70.3	1.18	1.99	67.3	0.98
+ t-4	32(0.2)4(0.2)	10 ⁻³	32	280	1.83	70.0	1.04	1.99	67.3	0.93
+ t-5	32(0.4)16(0.2)	10 ⁻³	32	240	1.83	70.6	1.11	2.10	67.9	1.25

* The number of neurons in successive dense layers is separated by a comma, with the dropout rate in parentheses if a dropout layer existed after a dense layer.

lagged variables were added this improvement only took place for the test set. Therefore, in order to reach a balance between the train and test fractions, the optimal model to classify the days as presenting thermal stratification or not was the model with up to 4 days-lagged variables. This model presents a testing accuracy of 96.0% and AUC of 0.99.

In order to get more insight, we represented the confusion matrix of this model, which gives information about how much the model confuses one class with the other one. As the value of the recall was 0.97 for the test set, it means that 97% of the times that the model determines that there exists stratification, it effectively exists. As shown in Table 3,

in the training set the trend to classify the reservoir as stratified in days that are labelled as non-stratified is similar than the trend to classify as non-stratified the days with stratification, however, in the test set, the model fails more in the identification of not-stratified days, in other words, there are more false positives.

A thorough look at the target data and the predictions reveals that this misclassification occurs both at the beginning and at the end of the stratification, but in different ways. As shown in Fig. 6, the formation of the thermocline is not as clear as its disappearance is, presenting some days of instability until the thermocline is formed. The model does not

Fig. 7. Real values of Z and the predicted ones with the optimal regression model.

Fig. 8. Averaged SHAP values for the model with only the original variables and the model with up to 3 days-lagged variables.

fail during the stable periods, but is not as accurate during the transition periods, especially during the formation of the thermocline. The worst year is 2019, when there were some days with intermittent thermal gradients above $0.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C m}^{-1}$ until the stratification finally stabilised.

3.3. Prediction of the depth of the thermocline

In this section the results of the regression models, trained and tested as described in section 2.5.3.2, are presented. They were used to infer the value of Z using only meteorological, storage state and flow downstream of the dam data as input. Table 4 contains the best set of hyperparameters found for each set of variables, together with the results from the training on the whole train data set and testing on unseen data. The Table follows the same structure than Table 2, with the only difference in the metrics used to assess the performance of the models. In addition to the MAE, its percentile within the errors of the same data subset and its median (P_{50}) have been also included. They allow assessing how the MAE is distributed.

According to the results, the training MAE decreases with the addition of lagged variables, but this leads to overfitting as the test error does not decrease to the same extent. The percentiles of the training and test errors reveal that approximately two thirds of the observations present an error lower than the MAE, in fact the median of the errors is between 30 and 50% lower than the MAE. Considering the best model that with the lowest test error, they would be the models with up to 3 or 4 days-lagged variables, the latter being a bit overfitted. Therefore, the selected

model is the one with up to 3 days-lagged variables.

Fig. 7 presents the real and predicted data for both training and test subsets, obtained with the model including up to 3 days-lagged variables as input. In the test subset, the errors that are higher than the MAE have been depicted darker than the errors that are lower. This allows discerning that the model performance is poorer at calculating the depth of the thermocline at the beginning and at the end of the stratified season. In general, the higher discrepancies occur when the thermocline is located deepest, specially in 2020 and 2022.

4. Discussion

One of the most concerning issues in the use of ML and DL models in experimental sciences is their interpretability. In fact, it is a buoyant research field nowadays. Among the techniques that have arisen to enhance the interpretability of the models, it is found the calculation of the SHAP values, which are represented in Fig. 8 for the optimal regression model designed in this study (which includes up to 3-days lagged variables); accompanied by the SHAP values for the model that contains only contemporary features. This allows comparing the situations where the temporal dimension is included or not. It is remarkable that in both cases the most important variables are those related to the water level, the average air temperature and the daily average irradiance. In the case of the model with lagged variables, the water level three days before the target day is the most important variable. It is coherent with the reduction in the MAE that occurred from the model with up to 2 days-lagged variables to the one with up to 3 days. This suggests that not only the water level is an important variable, but also the speed at which it changes. The following variable in terms of its contribution to the model performance is the average irradiance in the day before, followed by the same in the previous day. Among the other variables, the average air temperature in the day before the target day has also a high relative importance. In the model with only contemporary features, the importance of the level is particularly high, followed by the daily average temperature, the daily average irradiance and the maximum air temperature. The other variables have a much lower relative importance. In the El Val reservoir, the water level drops by about 10 m every summer, except in 2018, coinciding with the time when the thermocline moves to deeper layers. In fact, in 2018, when the level only dropped about 2 m, the thermocline only reached a depth of 20 m. As told before, this is attributed to the release of water through the bottom outlet, which in addition to decrease the level of the reservoir, it generates a current that drives warm water from the surface to deeper layers. This reveals the usefulness of this tool to assess the impact of different reservoir management strategies on the thermocline dynamics. In both models the less important variables are those related to the outflow, the rain and the wind. Regarding the outflow, a possible explanation is that it is redundant with the water level. The rain, which

Fig. 9. SHAP values for each observation and variable for the model with only the original variables (A) and the model with up to 3 days-lagged variables (B).

is weak most of the times (< 1 mm), seems to have practically no effect on the thermal behaviour which is in agree with Liu et al. (2020). Finally, regarding the wind, it also has a weak impact on the models. This is attributed to several reasons. Firstly, the wind speed registered in the weather station is normally low, reaching a maximum of 3.82 m s^{-1} with a mean value of 1.24 m s^{-1} . Secondly, the morphology of the reservoir, with a relatively small surface but high depth, makes the thermal profile less sensitive to the wind effect, in accordance with that stated by Wang et al. (2024c).

For a deeper understanding of the model outputs, Fig. 9 shows the plots of the SHAP values for each observation in the top ten variables for each model. The individual values make it possible to see whether a given observation produces an upward or downward change in the target variable as a function of its value. Regarding the water level, in both models the highest impact is achieved by the lowest values, which result in an increase in the depth of the thermocline. This is coherent with the fact that the lowest water levels occur by the end of the summer (see Fig. A8), when the thermocline is located in deep layers. Regarding the daily average irradiance, high values are related with a decrease of the thermocline depth, while low values result in an increase of its depth. The highest values of daily average irradiance take place by June, when the solar path is longer and the Sun occupies the highest positions. In this period, the formation of the thermocline is very recent and is still located in the upper layers. Similarly, average daily temperature is associated with a deepening of the thermocline only in a few observations. This is coherent with the findings of Bernd and Frank (2014), Noori et al. (2023) and Wang et al. (2024c) regarding the low correlation between the main driving forces of the thermal stratification (solar radiation and air temperature) and the deep layers water temperature. As shown with the developed ML models, in most of the observations the impact of the main driving forces is associated with a decrease of the depth of the thermocline, a process that takes place when it is still located in the upper layers. Wang et al. (2023c) found that warming temperatures caused little impact on the depth of stratification in summer, which is in accordance with our results.

The analysis of the impact of the different variables would vary from one study site to another, depending on the mechanisms that govern the thermal stratification in each study site. Nonetheless, this study reveals that often freely available variables, such as meteorological data and water level, can be used to obtain useful predictions by means of simple and easy to implement methods such as ML or DL models. Despite their black box nature, there are ways to elucidate the role of the different variables in the predictions obtained. Although the level of insight is not as high as that obtained with numerical models, these ML models allow a useful approach that can fill the gap in cases where information such as bathymetry is not available, or simply when a quick assessment is needed.

In fact, despite the momentum of publishing data on various topics in open format and in compliance with the FAIR principles, the main limitation of this framework is the availability of data to train a new model for each new study site. Regarding the topic of this work, we have identified the dataset by Pilla et al. (2022) about the thermal structure of 153 lakes around the world, that could be used to assess the performance of this framework in different climatic areas. Nonetheless, the non-supervised clustering method *k-means* has demonstrated to be able to make clusters that have a high agreement with the situations of mixing and stratification. This would open the door to apply this approach to any reservoir and not only to those with an intensive monitorization like El Val reservoir.

5. Conclusions

In this work, a framework to design ML models to detect the period of thermal stratification and to calculate the depth of the thermocline is presented. This framework relies only on data that are usually available for many reservoirs, such as meteorological data and storage state data,

but considering the site-specificity of ML models, other relevant variables, like input stream flows, could be included as well when they are available. It is revealed that a non-supervised model can be useful to estimate when the reservoir is stratified or not, in the absence of data from physico-chemical monitoring of the water mass. In addition, clustering of the available data on the driving forces associated with thermal stratification was useful in determining the thermal gradient to be used as a threshold for determining whether or not the reservoir is stratified.

Next, the classification models had a very good performance, with test accuracies always above 93%. In addition, the models are not biased towards any of the classes considered in the classification. The beginning and the end of the thermal stratification period can be located accurately, which also allows estimating the duration of the stratified period.

The best regression model to calculate Z had a test MAE of 1.99 m with a median of 0.98 m. The highest errors are mainly attributed to the process of migration of the thermocline to deeper layers during the release of water through the bottom outlet.

The information provided by these models is useful for water resources managers that need a quick assessment of the position of the thermocline, as well as for long-term studies, like those evaluating different climate change scenarios. Furthermore, due to the wide availability of the data used as input in the models, the framework presented in this work could be transferred to many other reservoirs where temperature vertical profile data were available to calculate the target variables.

It's worth noting that this tool can be used as a standalone tool to inform the decision makers, as well as a complementary tool that, together with other methods like in-situ measurements, remote sensing, and numerical modelling, may be used for more accurate and comprehensive assessment of the thermocline characteristics in reservoirs. As an example of hybrid modelling, the serial combination of the hereby presented models with other knowledge-based models could be of great interest in the development of wider models like digital-twins.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

María Castrillo: Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Fernando Aguilar:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Daniel García:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

All data used to conduct this study have been obtained from open data sources. Specifically, as mentioned in Section 2.1, the data were gathered from the web page of the Ebro Automatic Water Quality Information System (SAICA Ebro) and the web page of the Ebro Automatic Hydrographic Information System (SAIH Ebro), in particular from the weather station of El Val (code EM71), the monitoring station of the reservoir storage state (code E071) and the Queiles River gauge station (code A174).

The pre-processed dataset as it is fed to the models and the Python code to facilitate the implementation of this framework is available in GitHub (https://github.com/IFCA-Advanced-Computing/Thermocline_prediction) and Zenodo (doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11479475>).

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Appendix A. Appendix

Table A1

Statistical descriptors of the numerical variables.

	Air Temp Max	Air Temp Min	Air Temp Avg	Wind	Rad Max	Rad Avg	Rain	Level	Flow
count	1667	1667	1667	1667	1667	1667	1667	1667	1667
mean	20.01	8.49	13.79	1.24	364.58	78.99	1.27	613.80	0.82
min	-0.90	-6.60	-3.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	604.76	0.09
Q25	13.30	3.95	8.11	1.00	258.50	39.31	0.00	610.70	0.19
Q50	19.00	8.10	12.98	1.18	389.00	72.70	0.00	614.60	0.67
Q75	27.10	13.40	19.67	1.43	478.50	116.89	0.20	617.13	1.27
max	41.70	21.90	32.27	3.82	720.00	175.85	88.50	619.88	2.83
std	8.62	5.78	7.08	0.41	133.41	44.42	4.63	4.12	0.68

Fig. A1. Evolution of the daily maximum temperature (°C) along the 5 years under study.

Fig. A2. Evolution of the daily minimum temperature (°C) along the 5 years under study.

Fig. A3. Evolution of the daily average temperature (°C) along the 5 years under study.

Fig. A4. Evolution of the daily average wind speed (m s⁻¹) along the 5 years under study.

Fig. A5. Evolution of the daily maximum irradiance (Wm^{-2}) along the 5 years under study.

Fig. A6. Evolution of the daily average irradiance (Wm^{-2}) along the 5 years under study.

Fig. A7. Evolution of the daily cumulative precipitation (L m^{-2}) along the 5 years under study.

Fig. A8. Evolution of the reservoir water level (m.a.s.l.) along the 5 years under study.

Fig. A9. Evolution of the Queiles river flow ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$) along the 5 years under study.

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